

Feature selection for genomic prediction of perennial ryegrass forage quality

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Abstract. Feature selection enables the identification of important SNPs for development of low-density genotyping assays for use in genomic selection. The objective of this study was to evaluate genetic algorithms for feature selection prior to genomic prediction of forage digestibility in *Lolium perenne*. The reference population consisted of 1800 genotypes from 30 diploid populations consisting of 10 cultivars, 8 full-sib families, 8 half-sib families and 4 ecotypes. Plants were established in a spaced plant field trial and forage dry matter digestibility (DMD) was determined with near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS). Genomic predictions based on genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) data were performed on a full marker dataset and reduced marker subsets. Genetic algorithms enabled us to select subsets of features with predictive ability comparable to the entire SNPs set. While further optimization is required, identifying key predictor variables may enable selection for forage quality using inexpensive marker systems.

Keywords: Genomic Selection, Plant Breeding, Feature selection

1 Background

Genomic selection (GS) has the potential to accelerate genetic gain for complex forage traits in perennial ryegrass breeding programs [5]. However, genotyping at high densities to calculate Genomic Estimated Breeding Values (GEBVs) on selection candidates can be cost prohibitive to apply GS routinely. Feature selection for development of low-density genotyping assays to calculate GEBVs might be a solution.

Genetic algorithm (GA) is a heuristic approach that mimics natural selection processes in nature, such as mutation, crossover and selection, for feature selection [6]. In this study, we evaluate the implementation of GA to select re-

duced number of SNP markers for prediction of forage DMD, without the loss of predictive ability.

2 Methods

The training population (1800 genotypes) consisted of 30 diploid perennial ryegrass populations comprising 60 genotypes each [1]. Plants were grown in two replicates. Quality data comes from the 1st cut of the 2015. NIRS calibrations were used to predict feed quality traits, including DMD [2]. Predicted quality values were averaged per genotype. Plants were genotyped-by-sequencing (GBS) as shown by Elshire et al. (2011) [3] and data analyzed as in Arojju et al. (2018) [1]. Genotypes with low sequencing coverage were eliminated. Markers with more than 25% missing data were removed and the missing data for markers that were retained in the analysis was mean imputed. Ridge regression best linear unbiased prediction (rrBLUP) was used for genomic prediction in R with the rrBLUP package [4] on a full set of markers (~18,000). Genomic prediction models were evaluated using Monte-Carlo cross-validation by randomly assigning plants into training (70%) and test (30%) sets (1,000 iterations). Predictive ability (PA) was determined as the Pearson's correlation coefficient between observed phenotypic value and predicted phenotype. Bias was evaluated by regressing observed phenotypic value on predictions.

A genetic algorithm was implemented in R to select subsets of features (SNPs) most relevant for genomic prediction. The implementation proceeded as follows: let U be a set that contains full SNPs dataset. For $n = 200$ SNPs (1% of a full set of markers, rounded up), $k = 50$ subsets of size n are randomly selected from U . For each k subset, genomic prediction with rrBLUP is performed using 10-fold cross-validation. Obtained predictive ability (PA), bias and interquartile range (IQR) are averaged over all folds. Next, subsets are ordered in descending order based on a score calculated as $0.5PA + 0.5(1 - IQR)$. Each subset (A) is paired with a randomly selected different (B) subset. Two random split sites are generated per subset and SNPs falling between split sites are exchanged between A and B , forming recombined A' and B' . Each marker in the recombined subsets can be substituted with a randomly selected marker (e.g. for A' new SNPs can be drawn from $U - A$), with mutation probability $p = 0.01$. New subsets are used as input for rrBLUP, with 10-fold cross-validation. The resulting marker subsets are ordered in descending order for calculated score, and first k subsets are kept for the next iteration. We used leave-one-population-out fold-validation to assess the performance of selected SNP subsets on unseen data: for each fold, (i.) the genetic algorithm was run on a training set excluding one population, (ii.) a prediction model was built on the training data, and (iii.) GA selected markers and full SNPs dataset were used to predict DMD values on unseen data. The PA and bias were calculated.

3 Results

The mean predictive ability and bias of 1,000 iterations of Monte-Carlo cross-validation for DMD for the full marker set was 0.42 and 1.0, respectively. In different runs of genetic algorithm, the best 200 SNP set from the initial 50 subsets would have a mean PA of around 0.32. After 10 iterations, the best subset (GA) would usually reach PA level of 0.4, with more iterations leading to overfitting. Under a more challenging leave-one-population-out validation, the PA varied greatly depending on the population being left out (Fig. 1), emphasizing the importance of a relationship between training and testing set. In the case of the genetic algorithm, the GA subset obtained lower mean PA, when used to predict DMD on unseen data, compared to a full SNPs dataset. In general, higher PA was obtained for populations that were genetically closer to populations from the training set.

Fig 1. Predictive ability and bias of marker subset selected by genetic algorithm (GA, 200 SNPs, 10 iterations) and a full dataset (17974 SNPs) under leave-one-population-out validation.

Further work will be done to optimize selection of the size of SNPs subsets and the genetic algorithm itself, to limit the risk of overfitting. Other plans include a comparison of the GA results with other feature selection methods, such as genome-wide association studies (GWAS), as well as a validation of predictive ability of selected SNPs subsets on the F2 populations. Identifying a small subset of features with high predictive ability will enable selection for forage quality using inexpensive marker systems.

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